

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING WRITING

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***Abstract:** this article is devoted to the role of pedagogical teaching technologies that contribute to improving writing competence. Moreover, pedagogical teaching technologies continue to assume increasing importance as tools that help teachers to facilitate teaching, one of the most challenging skills as writing.*

***Key words:** pedagogical teaching technologies, CTTRW, written language, technique, PRES-formula, SWOT-analysis.*

Writing is a complex skill that provides communication between people with the help of graphic signs system [1].

This is a productive activity whereby a person records his/her speech for transfer to others. Writing is one of the ways to develop our thoughts and ideas.

For many years, written language proficiency in a foreign language was not the goal of teaching due to the dominant position of spoken language and the complexity of writing (with a limited number of hours). Writing was only a means of teaching other types of skills that allowed students to better understand the program language material and as a means of development of learners' verbal skills and abilities. Meanwhile, written form of communication performs an important communicative function in modern society. Therefore, the attitude to writing and teaching students the ability to express their thoughts in written form have changed sharply.

In modern pedagogy, various pedagogical teaching technologies are used to promote the development of learners' written language. Pedagogical teaching technologies, unlike any other technologies, contribute to more effective learning, achieved by increasing interest and motivation of students to it.

Further, I would like to suggest several techniques that contribute to a significant increase learners' foreign language writing competence:

1.PRES-formula (Point-Reason-Example-Summary). The main goal of this technique is to build the capacity of learners to develop their own opinions in a

concise and succinct form, that is, according to the PRES formula, they must respond briefly, reasonably and set out their consideration on a given topic. Sometimes it's easier to trigger ourselves with Questions.

If it makes it easier for you, **PRES** can also be substituted with **What(Point), Why (Reason), How (Example/Explanation)** and **What If Summary/Suggestion/Call to Action**.

Example:

What: I love the color blue

Why: Because blue makes me feel calm and happy

How: When I'm looking at the blue sky, or the ocean, I am transported to a special place where I can forget all my worries and just relax

What if: So if you want some calm and escape from your worries, you might want to consider going to the beach and gaze in the ocean. The colors and the sound of the ocean will relax you.

You could Point or What or Why for your Opening, and use Summary for you Closing [3].

2. "Cinquain". This is a five-line poetic form. Its point is that information is summarized, at the same time, complex ideas, feelings are expressed with just some words proves that it develops the ability to synthesize information and express it succinctly. There have been many variations of the cinquain since its invention. To fully understand Cinquains, here is a description of one of the more popular form.

- The first line is one word.
- The second line contains two adjectives.
- The third line has three words ending in "ing."
- The fourth line has four or more words that make a complete sentence.
- The fifth line is one word.

Here is an example of this form of Cinquain:

Acrobats

Acrobats

Flexible, amusing

Flipping, twirling, jumping

They make me laugh

Performers [2]

3. SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) -analysis. The purpose of this method is to develop students' skills to conduct a differentiated

analysis on a given problem revealing advantages, negative characteristics, opportunities and negative consequences of the analyzed topic.

The implementing of the above techniques in the framework of the CTTRW (Critical Thinking Through Reading and Writing) technology in the process of improving foreign language written competence of learners in teaching English contributes to the development of analytical skills, self-search information, building a logic loop, making a weighted and reasoned decision, reaching the level of conscious competence of learners.

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